

QUEEN OF ETERNITIES - BETWEEN CULTURES AND TEMPORALITIES

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Abstract

La Reine Morte (1942) is a play which dates back to one of the most referenced characters in Portuguese Literature. Works such as *Os Lusíadas* and *À Castro*, both from the 16th century, present her under the predominance of the lyrical gaze. Such character can awaken the most varied performances through its symbolic poignancy. The themes: "the crown of death" and "dying for love" move between the sacred and the profane and this intrigue draws the intense and instigating atmosphere. However, behind both works, relationships are woven between political and national forces that articulate and contextualize each character. In the first, there is the praise of national culture; in the second, the representation of power and its consequences. Investigating how the french author, Henry de Montherlant, traces these issues back within another conception, contemporary to the 20th century, is the objective of this study. The importance of dialogues as a way of addressing the major themes presented in the narrative is highlighted: love, death, and power. The study focuses on the representation of "Inês de Castro" and "Ferrante", when describing the dialogic composition and positioning, both on the physical and symbolic levels, that both occupy in the work. Thus, it is possible to observe the approximations and distances in the speeches between them and the articulation between the other voices produced in the text. For that, we resort to the notes of Pavis (2008) about theatrical composition; to Rosenfeld's (1985) observations about genres in theater, and to Vernant's (2006) reflections aimed at myth and symbol based on the Greeks and their developments. This bibliography offers subsidies for the articulation of the proposal, but they do not contain the possibilities for reading the piece, nor its aesthetic-communicative strength.

Keywords: Dialogue; Theater; Symbol.

1. INTRODUCTION

Written at a time when the world was threatened by Hitler's might, the French work resonates with the Revolution of yesteryear. The play refers to the Portuguese narrative and brings current issues to its period of creation, such as absolute and undeniable power, fought bravely by an antagonistic and foreign force. This creation speaks to today, when thinking about how much the role of the state and the individual need to be reformulated so that a

better world exists. It is worth remembering a reflection that permeates the imagination of French civilization and which, possibly, is a text read by Henry de Montherlant. This is the famous *Discourse on the Origin and Foundations of Inequality among Men*.⁴ by Jean Jacques Rousseau.

Rousseau was not French, but by the time he wrote this speech he had already established a strong relationship with the country. The elite listen to your ideas and are influenced by them. By bringing the concept of citizen, it questions natural laws against political laws. At the beginning of the text, the following statement occurs:

If I had the happiness of being born among you, how could I meditate on the equality that nature has placed among men, and on the inequality that they have instituted, without thinking of the profound wisdom with which one and the other, happily combined in this State, concur. , in a way closer to the natural law and more favorable to society, to the maintenance of public order together with private satisfactions? (*My translation* - ROUSSEAU, 1754, p. 3).⁵

There is the imperative of a social order, which often prevents individual expressions. This is the primordial conflict that Rousseau denounces. The text continues in this tone and suggests the use of freedom as a right, but emphasizes that the subject should be prepared for it. The author illustrates the use of freedom in the following way: "(...) it is like consuming strong and succulent foods, generous wines, suitable for nourishing and fortifying the robust temperaments, which are used to them, but which end up ruining and intoxicating the reckless and weak who are definitely not ready." (*My translation* - ROUSSEAU, 1754, p. 4) .⁶In this way, duplicity is found in a single subject, whoever governs is a sovereign, as he needs to

⁴Original title: *Discourse on the origin and foundations of inequality among men*.

Publicações: *November -1755, October; dedication, 1754, June-October (additions); "The manuscript that Rousseau sent to the Academy of Dijon & disappeared from the archives of the said Academy." the Pleiade edition, t. III, pp. 1859-1860; fragments, Public and University Library of Geneva ms. Fr. 228, National Library, Paris, ms. Fr. 12,760, etc.; In Amsterdam, Marc Michel Rey, 1755, etc.; the Pleiade edition, t. III, pp. 109-223. Du Peyrou/Moultou 1780-1789 quarto edition, t. I, pp. 1-176.]*

⁵ " *Having had the good fortune to be born among you, how could I meditate on the equality that nature has placed between men, and on the inequality that they have instituted, without thinking of the profound wisdom with which one and the other, happily combined in this State, contribute, in the manner closest to natural law and most favorable to society, to the maintenance of public order and the happiness of individuals? (ROUSSEAU, 1754, p. 3).*

⁶ " *For it is with freedom as with those solid and succulent foods, or those generous wines, suitable to Nourish and fortify the robust temperaments which are accustomed to them, but which overwhelm, ruin and intoxicate the weak and delicate who do not 'are not made there'. (ROUSSEAU, 1754, p. 4).*

exercise the greater good for society and, at the same time, is also a citizen like the others, who aims at his own choices and interests.

Based on this conception, the author reaches a very relevant conclusion: the ideal would be for there to be a loving union between these two positions. Like a marriage that provides for a common good: "Citizens, the fate of your sex will always govern ours. Happy! when your chaste power, exercised only in the conjugal union, makes itself felt only in the glory of the State and in public happiness." (*My translation* - ROUSSEAU, 1754, p. 9).⁷. The principle of fidelity as a consequence of love is what would sustain this ideal world. To be faithful to oneself would be to be faithful to the State and vice versa. In such harmony, there would be no political crime. This utopia sustained by desire, which draws a possibility, albeit distant.

The drama that arises in *La Reine Morte* by Henry de Montherlant is this imbalance or the harsh conception that the common good is not compatible with the individual good. But desire is always latent. The character recovers this ideal and his death is the postponement of effectiveness.

Now, in a period when freedom is threatened, the social good ends up being annulled in itself. For the author who experienced the Great War up close, as in 1916 he participated in the auxiliary service of the armed forces, being wounded and decorated. This experience ends up being reflected in the works⁸ *Songe* , autobiographical novel, and *Funeral song for the dead by Verdun* , in which he brings up the question of heroism, a theme that extends to other titles *Les Bestiaires*, *Les Olympiques*, *Aux fontaines du wish*, *La Petite infante de Castille* , etc.)

Around the Mediterranean he wrote essays from the defeat of 1940 and the years of the Occupation: *The September Equinox*, *The June Solstice*, *Texts under an occupation - 1940-1944* , *Notebooks - 1940-1944* . In these writings he presents a less heroic and more tragic conception of reality. In this context, Montherlant writes *La Reine Morte* at the request of the then administrator of *La Comédie Française* - this cultural space that represented, during the years of German occupation in the country, an intense reactionary production. The text takes on another guise, as it has existed since the 16th century written by the Spaniard

⁷"Citizens, the fate of your sex will always be to govern ours. Happy! when your chaste power exercised only in the conjugal union, is felt only for the glory of the State & the public happiness." . (ROUSSEAU, 1754, p. 9).

⁸Available at: < <https://www.academie-francaise.fr/les-immortels/henry-de-montherlant> >>. Accessibility: 13 Set 2021.

Luis Vélez de Guevara. If the first version was produced in the Golden Century, the second presents the perspective of a time of ruins. Between one period and another is the symbol of inordinate power and flawed justice. Death being a relevant factor for both productions. Vaudoier himself had written his version of *La Reine Évanouie*. And it is with her that Montherlant talks more closely when he dedicates the play to the friend who proposes him to write:

My dear friend (...) my works always come out of an inner need, more or less deep. For the first time in my life, a theme was proposed by the subject: the author of *La Reine Évanouie* gave me the purpose of *La Reine Morte*. Instead of making it, in my own way, what I chose to learn, I took what it offered me: I am still surprised. With a lucky guess, you had delved into a matter that would be viable for me: I would only have to let it rest on my heart, so that it germinated there. guesswork ? ⁹(MONTHERLANT, 1942, p.15 - *My translation*).

It is noticed that there is a very intimate relationship between the referenced work and the creation of Montherlant. But one can glimpse the differences by choosing the adjective that characterizes the Queen. “*Évanouie*” carries the connotation of fainting, that is, she who is asleep or unconscious - here the end is not expressed; there is a fading that determines the precarious situation. In “*Death*” the queen is determined with all her totality of meaning: her death carries within it the denunciation of the crime reconstituted through this closure. As a symbolic power, death guards complete existence.

Still in the dedication, there is the expression about what was modified: “By going beyond the limits of the sonnet, you left me in a fresh world for me, where I could find a new reason for liveliness”. ¹⁰(MONTHERLANT, 1942, p.16 – *My translation*). It is through the free form that the word is expressed. The voices will echo, no longer in the amplified architecture of the classic verse, which enhances and elevates the meanings through the harmonious sound. It is in the concreteness of the word, where the concepts are even in the terms and in the syntax free of aesthetic elaboration to commit to the urgency of the unfeasible, unexpected and undesirable contexts for these characters. The environments are

⁹ *My dear friend, My works always spring from an inner necessity, more or less profound. For the first time in my life, a subject was proposed as a subject: the author of La Reine Vanouie handed me the subject of La Reine Morte. Instead of taking, in my fashion, what I chose to take, I took what was offered to me: I am still amazed. With a kind of divination, you had pricked on a matter which was suitable for me: I had only to let it rest on my heart, so that it germinated there. Divination? (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p.15).*

¹⁰ *By sparing me the ringing of the doorbell, you released me into a world fresh to me, where to find a new reason for snorting. (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 16)*

inhospitable for them, however, it is the place where they are inserted, and it would not be the wisest choice to flee.

From this brief contextual presentation, there is a need to study the piece and its vocal power. Thus, the approximations and departures in the speeches between the main characters: Inês and Ferrante and the articulation between the other voices produced in the text are evident. In order to do so, we resort to the notes of Pavis (2008) regarding theatrical composition; to Rosenfield's (1985) observations on genres in theater, and to Vernant's (2006) reflections, aimed at myth and symbol from the Greeks and their developments. This bibliography offers subsidies for the articulations of the proposal, but they do not end the possibilities of reading the play, nor its aesthetic-communicative force.

1.1 POSSIBILITIES AND IMPOSSIBILITIES AS FACES OF THE SAME CROWN

The work features the following characters: Ferrante, king of Portugal, 60 years old; Prince D. Pedro, 26 years old; Egas Coelho, Prime Minister; Alvar Gonçalves, counselor; Don Christoval, former governor of the prince; The Great Amiral; Dino del Moro, page of the king; Don Eduardo, secretary of the hand, Don Manoel Ocayo, A Infante de Navarre - D. Bianca - 17 years old; the Battle Captain, two pages of the king, Lieutenant Martins; Ines de Castro, 26 years old. In this provision, there are some issues to be considered: the first is age; the second the power relations between them. In addition, the issue of intimacy that these characters describe with each other must be considered.

In addition to more peripheral relationships, such as those of the pages and their lords; the counselors and the king; the ones that most provoke tensions stand out. Those built in medium conflicts are the following: The Infante and Pedro, Pedro and his father, The Infante and Inês; and the most intense dialogues are between Ferrante and Inês. Thus, the narrative described brings the promised son to the Infante de Navarre who ends up establishing a relationship with Inês de Castro in secret, in a marriage, from which a child is generated. Ferrante, to ensure the power of the State, decides to kill Inês. However, he also finds himself facing death: there is a crisis of conscience that the king cannot bear. This is the conflict established by the dialogues.

From the moment we recognize the characters' intimate yearnings, we can visualize their condition in the face of the feelings they express. Rosenfield (1985), in a very didactic way, conceptualizes: "Lyricism tends to be the immediate shaping of the experiences of an I

in the encounter with a world, without interposing events distended in time (as in Epic and Drama).” (ROSENFELD, 1985, p. 22).

In the play, the two highlighted characters are faced with a gigantic world. The king, faced with a kingdom and its obligations, has the obligation to control everything. Upon realizing that this is impossible, it is tormented by the pressure of other government officials who request decision-making and constant accountability, which exerts great influence on its procedures. However, he simply accepts all these conditions, without renouncing power, even though he acts much more in favor of the appearance of governing, than exercising command attitudes properly speaking. This makes him very powerless. At first, one can contact in several passages a king who cynically puts his inappropriate position and who justifies his actions through sentimental expression.

On the other hand, Inês, who, regardless of the consequences, expresses her condition through emotions in each gesture printed in her words. In such a way that what she feels becomes much more important than her own life. There is no attempt at blunt defense, the character does not even pose as a heroine, much less as a victim. Her actions do not go beyond the expression of herself and her love.

They are two characters empty of actions, without a strong impulse to change their destiny. However, the force of his words reveals these absurd positions. It is necessary to pay attention to what motivates the expression of these feelings.

Rosenfield, emphasizes: “The 'immediate' verbal manifestation of an emotion or a feeling is the starting point of the Lyric”. (ROSENFELD, 1985, p. 22). This immediate connotation is what differentiates them, as it only occurs with Inês, since she has no intention of preservation, which ends up exposing her greatly, to the point of being killed due to being coherent with her feeling. On the contrary, the king plays a constant game, between expressions and concealments in order to remain in the position of governor.

The dialogues brought by the author are very well constructed, because through them the drama opens up in conflicts, revealing the themes with their possibilities and impossibilities, with the presentation of the perspectives and positions of both characters. These themes are placed and discussed in several fragments.

At the beginning of the play, the reader/spectator already has access to Ferrante, because like the other characters, he puts himself through his own lines. However, Inês is known through what people say about her. When entering an environment to which they do not belong, their presence has repercussions. Beforehand, we traced his portrait from these

other perspectives. However, in act I – scene V, the first meeting between Inês and Ferrante takes place. Upon receiving her, he introduces her himself: “Here is Dona Inês in front of me. Your fame has warned me in your favor. Your air, your salute, even your dress, everything confirms to me that you are of good origin. And so I do not doubt that you would not find it in yourself to match the circumstances in which we have placed ourselves.” (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 53 - *My translation*).¹¹

There is in his speech an accusation behind these praises. By choosing the expression “equalize”, the king suggests a coup possibly practiced by Inês, that of acquiring a noble position. There is, through this statement, the attempt to unmask. It is the moment when she has to report her love affair to the king and present arguments to defend her. However, before that happens, the king predicts that she could possibly lie and goes on with his arguments:

Lying is second nature to my Great Ones. Just as they prefer to obtain through threat what they could obtain through sweetness, to obtain through fraud what they could obtain by right, they prefer to obtain through hypocrisy what would be acquired for them all so easily by Francoism: it is the ordinary genius of events. And you, let's go! We will! You would have quickly taken the taste. Also, it is better to lie to others than to lie to yourself. (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 55 – *My translation*).¹²

There is a contradiction in this argument. There is the presentation of the social necessity of lying, but with the observation that one should not lie to oneself. With this, in addition to alerting Inês to the naturalness of detecting a lie, there is also an outburst, with this caveat. Thus, lying is seen as a means or a strategy of action against the other, which can lead to a faulty act, if this action is reported to oneself. What we can infer from this explanation is that lying always causes harm. And if perhaps Inês does not recognize that she is lying, she would be deceiving herself. In this way, he justifies his act of condemning her.

¹¹ "So here is donã Inès, in front of me. Your fame had warned me in your favour. Your demeanor, your countenance, even your clothes, everything confirms to me that you are from a good place. And so I have no doubt that you find in yourself enough to equal the circumstances in which you have placed us." (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 53).

¹² Lying is second nature to my Elders. Just as they prefer to obtain by threat what they could obtain by gentleness, to obtain by fraud what they could obtain by righteousness, they prefer to obtain by hypocrisy what would be obtained just as easily by franchising: it is the ordinary genius of courts. And yourself, come on! come on ! you would quickly have taken a liking to it. Besides, it is less important not to lie to others than not to lie to oneself. (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 55).

On the other hand, Inês justifies herself, as the king expected, but the way she presents her perspective ends up challenging him, due to her blunt tone. She says smiling: “If I lied, I would quickly get lost in my lies. Possibly they would placate me.” (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 55 – *My translation*).¹³ In this subjective speech there is the statement that lying would only have negative effects for Inês. Thus, by telling the truth, the possibility that any injury is erased. has a defined look, while the king implies a double perspective.

In act II - scene II, there is the conception of life as a repetitive exercise. It can be said that habits end up becoming the source of benefits and harm. The power of the king is observed as an obligation difficult to bear: “And the reign is like charity: if we have started, we must continue. Which is heavy, often.” (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 97- *My translation*).¹⁴ The concept of donation is observed, which does not provide a benefit to whoever commits the action, but to whom it is intended. Such a comparison is not valid, because the king, when taking over the government, has the benefits: money and the maximum authority. But that means a burden for him. The charitable person gives himself voluntarily and the regrets for such an action become small in the face of the good provided. When we reflect on Rousseau's position, in which the good of the nation should be the good of the individual, the king ends up contradicting this thought.

Inês, in her everyday attitudes and even on the verge of death, values all the actions she performs: “It's always the same thing, and yet it seems to me that it's always the first time. And there are also actions that are always the same, and yet, each time we perform them, it is as if God descended to earth.” (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 97 – *My translation*)¹⁵. Finding novelty in your everyday attitudes means living fully. Being alive is expressed in the divine figure, that is, the creator comes towards the creature. In this way, human eventualities dialogue with the expressions of the divine. Thus, Inês values every moment, as she visualizes the grandeur of the world and of life itself. As if in each act, even if repeated, there was

¹³*“If I was lying, I would quickly get confused in my lies. Maybe that's all that stops me.” (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 55).*

¹⁴*“And the reign is like charity: when one has begun, one must continue. But that is heavy, sometimes. ” (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 97).*

¹⁵*“It's always the same thing, and yet it seems to me that it's always the first time. And there are also acts that are always the same, and yet, each time you do them, it's as if God were coming down to earth.” (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 97).*

something greater than herself, to the point that this inexplicable something that she feels and does not justify, awakens her to the singularities that are renewed at every moment.

Even in relation to the plane of feelings, Ferrante ends up differing from Inês, when she reports: “Most affections are nothing more than habits or duties that we don't have the courage to break. ” (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 104 – *My translation*)¹⁶. Such a statement even implies affection towards the child. For him, everything takes on the connotation of figuration. All his actions are intended for the eyes of others, so that he is always assuring what is expected of him, which, consequently, guarantees his power before others and his fragility before himself. It is observed that the feeling of emptiness is something that accompanies you permanently.

Inês also has a feeling that always accompanies her. She confesses it in the first scene of the following act: “Always, Lord, always this gloomy presentiment” (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 135 – *my translation*).¹⁷Here, the repetition of the word “always” is found, which ends up intensifying the constancy of that feeling of finitude that accompanies his life. It is the certainty of death, the fragility of life that puts her in a situation of valorization of her experiences. The character in open dialogue with the king is gradually becoming more aware that the sentence that the ruler will give him, in fact, is already determined by his own existence. With death in perspective, there is an awakening to the power of presentification. Being alive gives a new meaning to death: if, on the one hand, it is decisive, in the sense of interrupting life; on the other hand, existence itself needs to be valued in order to assert its infinity. So, it doesn't matter how much time you have left before death comes, what matters is that this time exists and that's enough.

The theme intensifies even more when the king himself confesses his physical-emotional weakness. However, for him the end is seen as something feared, but desired. Faced with the devaluation of one's own existence, dying becomes a relief : “Then, often, my heart stops... When it starts beating again, I am totally surprised to find myself alive, and a little disappointed.” (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 136 – *My translation*).¹⁸If Inês feels frightened by the certainty of death; Ferrante is terrified, to the point of denying his own

¹⁶ " Most affections are only habits or duties that one does not have the courage to break" (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 104).

¹⁷"Always, Lord, always that dark foreboding." (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 135).

¹⁸"So, often, my heart stops ... When it starts beating again, I am quite surprised to find myself alive, __, and a little disappointed. " (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 136).

feelings to fight it. As he says in scene VI of the third act: "But I believed very well that one of the best guarantees of long life is to be insensitive and incapable; behold, a breastplate against death." (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 97 – *My translation*)¹⁹. With that, behind these words there is the experience of emotions as a wear and tear. However, we realize that denial is not possible. Because when he is insensitive, other feelings end up dominating him, such as the feeling of torment, sadness and emptiness.

Disappointed with his heir, who does not think about maintaining power and acts out of love, he questions his interlocutor if the child she was expecting did not meet his expectations. And with poignancy Inês replies:

Yes, intoxicating. He will be called Dionysus. My little son with unbelievable eyebrows, handsome and fat, as boys are. Ask me to fight him, to dance with him. That you can't stand being touched. Let an excess of pleasure make you sigh. And if he is not beautiful, I will love him even more to console him and ask his forgiveness for having dreamed that he was different. (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 168).²⁰

The figure of Dionysus is brought to the fore to bring the greatest possible disposition to life. Getting drunk, in this context, means feeling incessantly, without holding back. To observe the rhythm of life is to conceive of it as permanent, greater than the subject himself. That's why she recognizes the breach of expectations as a possibility, which must be embraced and not rejected or ignored. Her son, a power of life: this is the legacy that Inês, on the verge of death, would like to leave for the world.

In scene VII of act III, the day before she dies, Inês continues with life flooding her perspective: "What a pity. But the night is clear and starless. Look. It will be a beautiful day tomorrow: the sky is full of stars." (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 179 – *My translation*).²¹The certainty that life goes on is a glimpse of its power and the smallness of the subject. And that provokes a look, albeit sad, clear and coherent. While Ferrante torments himself and tells about the dream he had, thus mixing consciousness with unconsciousness:

¹⁹"But I would willingly believe that one of the best guarantees of long life is to be callous and incompetent; that is a breastplate against death." (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 154).

²⁰Yes, intoxicating. His name will be Dionis. My little boy with incredible eyelashes, both handsome and rude, as boys are. Who asks that we fight with him, that we dance with him. Who can't stand being touched. That an excess of pleasure makes you sigh. And, if he is not handsome, I will love him even more to console him and ask his forgiveness for having wanted him to be other than he is. (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 168).

²¹"Hardly. But the night is clear and without pitfalls. Look. The weather will be fine tomorrow: the sky is full of stars." (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 179).

Ferrante

All these worlds where Redemption has not passed... Do you see the ladder?

Inês

Jacob's ladder, that?

Ferrante

No, not at all: the ladder from hell to heaven. All my life I have made this path incessantly; always going up and down , from hell to heaven. When, with all my sins, I lived covered by the divine hand. Still a strange thing.

Inês

Oh! There is a star that goes out...

Ferrante

It will light up elsewhere.

(MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 179 – *My translation*)²².

Jacob's ladder is an important reference to represent the dialogue between God and men. However, here, we have the representation of the contradiction, which implies the whole martyrdom of the king. Not power or lack thereof, not life, not death. Everything ends up being denied, by this guy who lives on appearances. And Inês, as she faces life, interrupts this delirium to show the dying star, which represents her death. While the king tries to look away, with the vain assertion that she will shine elsewhere. Such a statement is vain because it denies this death: if there is life on another plane, existence becomes permanent. But the affirmative does not occur with the ultimate belief; there is always the doubt that permeates all his representation.

²² *Ferrante*

All these worlds where the Redemption did not pass... Do you see the scale?

Ines

The scale ?

Ferrante

The ladder that reaches to the heavens.

Ines

Jacob's Ladder, perhaps?

Ferrante

Not at all: the ladder from hell to heaven. Me, all my life, I have made this journey incessantly; up and down all the time, from hell to heaven. Because, with all my sins, I nevertheless lived enveloped by the divine hand. Another strange thing.

Ines

Oh ! There is a fading star...

Ferrante

It will rekindle somewhere else.

(MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 179).

In the final scene, after ordering Inês to be killed, the king makes a speech, which implies a mixture of representations and which leads to its annulment. It is also the moment when he dies:

Gentlemen, I don't know how fate will judge Dona Inês' execution. It can be good, it can be bad. Whatever it is, here is the one who inspired it before anyone else. Wish her in answer before the king, my son. (Egas Coelho tries to flee. The assistants surround him and follow him). My God! In that breath I have left, before the sand comes back and crushes me, make it tear out that hideous knot of contradictions that are in me, so that, at least a moment, before that which serves as a safeguard ceases to exist, when it's time for my Judgment. __ Don't be afraid, and stay close to me, may it arrive... even if I die... God will make it up to you, God will make it up to you, my little brother... Much better and much worse ... (He gets up) __ When I resurrect... Oh! The sand! The sand! __ My God, have mercy on me! (He falls.). (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 186- *My translation*).²³

The king represents his death by confessing the death of Inês. Afraid of a final judgment, he justifies his actions and asks for forgiveness for the girl he had ordered killed. As well, his body rises and falls, giving vent and representation to the contradictions that it represents. God and the future take on meaning when he strips himself of his responsibilities to transfer to the creator and to destiny. Thus ends his power before the people.

2. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The play reports the lyricism through the appeal of life that each of the characters develops. Inês expresses her emotions through every word. And Ferrante, when trying to organize his ideas, falls into a lack of control. His death represents a riot of emotions; Inês's brings her whole life, as the end reveals individuality as a whole. Thus, it can be said that emotions are more important than actions. As Rosenfield argues about the lyrical genre:

²³ *Gentlemen, I don't know how the future will judge the execution of donã Inês. Maybe good, maybe bad. Be that as it may, here is the one who, above all else, inspired her. See that he answers to the king, my son. (Egas Coelho tries to flee. Attendants surround him and drag him away.) O my God! in this respite that remains to me, before the saber returns and crushes me, let it sever this terrible knot of contradictions which are in me, so that, for a moment at least before ceasing to be, I finally know What am I. (He pulls Dino del Moro in and holds him tight). May the innocence of this child be my safeguard when I appear before my Judge. __ Do not be afraid, and stay with me whatever happens ... even if I die God will give it back to you, God will give it back to you, my little brother ... Much better and much worse .. (He gets up.) _ When I resurrect... __ Oh! the sword ! the sword ! __ God, have mercy on me! (He collapses.). (MONTHERLANT, 1942, p. 186).*

“Being only the expression of an emotional state and not the narration of an event, the Pure Lyric poem does not clearly configure the main character (the lyrical I that expresses itself)”. (ROSENFELD, 1985, p. 22).

Dialogue is identified as the great character, according to what Pavis presents: “Dialogue between characters is often considered as the fundamental and exemplary form of drama. From the moment we conceive theater as the presentation of active characters, dialogue becomes "naturally" the privileged form of expression”. (PAVIS, 2008, p. 93).

All these emotions are related to the drama imprinted in the dialogues. There is no chorus that ponders or evaluates and even the didascalias are economical, bringing up the following argument from Rosenfield: “With the 'author' absent, the autonomous development of events is required in the drama, without the intervention of any mediator. , since the author entrusted the development of the action to characters placed in certain situations in the world in which it presents itself. (ROSENFELD, 1985, p. 30). The perspectives and opposing attitudes of the characters show us the world and its implications, because between living and dying, there is a range of possibilities that bring the reconsideration of power. The world presented is drawn naturally, because according to the theorist: “Dialogue seems to be the most apt way to show how the speakers communicate: the effect of reality is then much stronger, as the spectator has the sensation of watching a familiar form of communication between people”. (PAVIS, 2008, p. 93).

The myths “power”, “love” and “death” are discussed in the scenes presented. According to Vernat: “ In short, the mythologist seeks to reconstitute (...) a conception and an appreciation of the great forces which, in their mutual relations, in their just balance, dominate the world - the natural and the supernatural -, the men, society, making them what they should be.” (VERNAT, 2006, p. 26). The characters are fragile, as both the one who orders the kill and the victim have their purpose determined, while power and love remain through other subjects and other organizations - the reign and love relationships are in individualities and beyond. from them. Thus, the separation of the divine from the human occurs, returning to mythological conceptions.

The play brings out a disembodied crown by presenting a clumsy king who confesses to his victim, passing on an ideological authority through his imbalance. While the victim, whose body is crowned after death, had already become queen even before the final scene, as the balance and coherence she presents in the face of life and death, govern the feelings that reflect in her social actions.

3. REFERENCES

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